

Balancing Development and Environment: The Role of the National Green Tribunal

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Abstract:

The National Green Tribunal (NGT) of India plays a pivotal role in environmental protection by providing a specialized judicial platform for the swift resolution of environmental disputes. Established under the National Green Tribunal Act, 2010, the NGT integrates legal and technical expertise to address issues such as pollution control, forest conservation, and biodiversity protection. Its adjudicatory and appellate functions ensure strict enforcement of environmental laws and offer compensation for environmental damage. Landmark rulings, such as those involving Sterlite Industries and the Ganga River pollution, highlight the tribunal's proactive approach in enforcing regulations and holding violators accountable. By promoting public participation and developing robust environmental jurisprudence, the NGT significantly strengthens environmental governance in India. Despite challenges in implementation and balancing development with environmental concerns, the NGT remains crucial in advancing sustainable development and safeguarding ecological integrity.

Keywords: National Green Tribunal (NGT), Environmental protection, Environmental disputes, Environmental jurisprudence, Compensation, Environmental damage, Compensation, Sustainable development

Introduction:

Environmental degradation has become a significant concern globally, with its impacts felt across ecosystems, human health, and economic stability. The need for robust legal frameworks to address environmental issues has led to the establishment of specialized judicial bodies. One such body in India is the National Green Tribunal (NGT), established to expedite the resolution of environmental cases and ensure the effective enforcement of environmental laws. This article explores the role of the NGT in environmental protection, its structure and functions, significant case rulings, and its impact on environmental jurisprudence in India.

Historical Background

• Origins and Establishment

The National Green Tribunal (NGT) was established on October 18, 2010, through the enactment of the National Green Tribunal Act, 2010. The inception of the NGT was driven by the recognition of the growing complexity and specialized nature of environmental cases, which traditional courts were often ill-equipped to handle effectively and efficiently. The establishment of a dedicated environmental court aimed to provide a specialized platform for the swift resolution of environmental disputes. The NGT's creation was also intended to reinforce the "right to a healthy environment," as guaranteed under Article 21 of the Indian Constitution, which ensures the right to life and personal liberty, encompassing the right to a clean and healthy environment.

• Legislative Framework

The National Green Tribunal Act, 2010, provides the legislative framework for the NGT. This Act delineates the tribunal's jurisdiction, powers, and

procedures, specifying the types of cases it is authorized to adjudicate. The NGT has the authority to address issues related to environmental protection, the conservation of forests, and the sustainable management of natural resources. It is empowered to hear cases involving environmental laws, such as the Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974, the Forest (Conservation) Act, 1980, the Air (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1981, and the Environment (Protection) Act, 1986.

The NGT is mandated to provide effective and expeditious disposal of cases related to environmental protection and conservation, ensuring that legal rights pertaining to the environment are upheld. Its establishment marked a significant step towards strengthening environmental governance in India by ensuring that specialized and technical matters concerning the environment are addressed by a competent judicial body. The tribunal's decisions are binding and can be challenged only in the Supreme Court of India, underscoring its pivotal role in India's environmental justice system.

Structure and Jurisdiction

Composition:

The NGT comprises both judicial and expert members. The chairperson of the tribunal is a retired judge of the Supreme Court or a High Court. Alongside the chairperson, the tribunal includes other judicial members, who are also former judges of the Supreme Court or High Courts, and expert members with substantial experience in environmental and related fields. This combination ensures a balanced approach, integrating legal expertise with scientific and technical knowledge.

Jurisdiction:

The jurisdiction of the NGT is extensive, covering a wide range of environmental issues. It has the authority to hear cases related to:

- Water pollution
- Air pollution
- Forest conservation
- Biodiversity protection
- Waste management
- Environmental clearances for projects
- The tribunal is empowered to provide relief and compensation to victims of environmental damage, restitution of property damaged, and restitution of the environment.

Regional Benches:

To facilitate access to justice, the NGT operates through regional benches located in different parts of India. These benches are situated in New Delhi (Principal Bench), Bhopal, Pune, Kolkata, and Chennai. This regional distribution helps in addressing environmental issues specific to different regions and ensures that justice is not delayed due to geographical constraints.

Functions and Powers:

The National Green Tribunal (NGT) of India is vested with significant powers and functions aimed at addressing environmental disputes, ensuring compliance with environmental laws, and promoting sustainable development. Here's a detailed overview of its powers and functions:

- **Adjudicatory Role:**
 - **Specialized Tribunal:** The NGT serves as a specialized judicial body dedicated exclusively to environmental matters. It adjudicates on disputes relating to environmental laws, regulations, and policies.
 - **Principles of Natural Justice:** It operates on the principles of natural justice, ensuring fair and impartial adjudication of cases brought before it.
- **Preventive and Remedial Measures:**
 - **Injunctions and Directions:** The NGT has the authority to issue injunctions to prevent activities that are likely to cause environmental damage. It can also issue directions to mitigate existing environmental harm and restore ecological balance.
 - **Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA):** The tribunal can review and provide direction on projects undergoing Environmental Impact Assessment to ensure compliance with environmental norms and prevent adverse impacts.
- **Appellate Jurisdiction:**
 - **Review of Decisions:** As an appellate authority, the NGT hears appeals against decisions of central and state governments, and regulatory bodies under various environmental laws.

- **Scrutiny and Accountability:** It scrutinizes administrative decisions to ensure they align with environmental protection goals and legal requirements.

- **Environmental Compensation and Restoration:**

- **Polluter Pays Principle:** The NGT upholds the principle of "polluter pays," where those responsible for environmental damage are required to compensate affected parties.

- **Restoration of Environment:** It can direct measures for the restoration of the environment in cases where damage has occurred, aiming to mitigate adverse impacts and restore affected ecosystems.

- **Monitoring and Compliance:**

- **Monitoring Compliance:** The NGT monitors the implementation of its orders and directions to ensure compliance with environmental laws and its own directives.

- **Enforcement Actions:** It can enforce its orders through penalties, fines, or other measures to compel compliance and deter future violations.

- **Public Participation and Awareness:**

- **Public Hearings:** The NGT promotes public participation by conducting hearings that allow stakeholders, including affected communities, to voice concerns and provide input on environmental issues.

- **Awareness Campaigns:** It engages in awareness campaigns and educational activities to foster understanding of environmental laws and promote environmental stewardship.

- **Research and Expertise:**

- **Technical Expertise:** The NGT may seek expert opinion and technical advice to inform its decisions on complex environmental matters.

- **Research and Recommendations:** It conducts or commissions research and may make recommendations to governments and authorities on environmental policies and practices.

Significant Case Rulings:

The National Green Tribunal (NGT) has adjudicated numerous significant cases since its establishment, addressing a wide range of environmental issues. Here are some notable cases decided by the NGT:

Sterlite Industries (India) Ltd. Case:

In the Sterlite Industries (India) Ltd. case, the National Green Tribunal (NGT) ordered the closure of Sterlite's copper smelter plant in Tuticorin, Tamil Nadu, in 2013 due to severe environmental violations. The plant was found to be causing significant air and water pollution, which led to adverse health effects on the local population. Despite multiple public protests and documented environmental harm, Sterlite continued operations without necessary environmental clearances. The

NGT's ruling highlighted its commitment to stringent enforcement of environmental laws and prioritizing public health and ecological integrity over industrial interests.

Art of Living Foundation Case:

In the Art of Living Foundation case, the National Green Tribunal (NGT) imposed a fine on the foundation for environmental damage caused by the World Culture Festival held in March 2016 on the Yamuna floodplains in Delhi. The event led to significant ecological damage, including soil compaction and disruption of the river's ecosystem. The NGT directed the foundation to pay ₹5 crore as an interim environmental compensation and mandated the restoration of the affected area. This case underscored the NGT's role in holding organizations accountable for large-scale environmental violations and protecting natural habitats.

Ganga Pollution Case:

In the Ganga Pollution case, the National Green Tribunal (NGT) issued several directives to address the severe pollution in the Ganga River. The tribunal ordered industries along the river to install effluent treatment plants and mandated municipalities to prevent the discharge of untreated sewage into the river. The NGT's comprehensive action plan included measures for waste management, riverbank restoration, and continuous monitoring of pollution levels. The tribunal's proactive stance has been crucial in efforts to rejuvenate the Ganga, highlighting its commitment to enforcing environmental regulations and protecting one of India's most important water bodies.

Yamuna River Pollution Case:

In the Yamuna River Pollution case, the National Green Tribunal (NGT) issued multiple orders to tackle the severe pollution in the Yamuna River. The tribunal mandated the installation of sewage treatment plants, restricted industrial discharges, and prohibited the dumping of solid waste into the river. The NGT also directed authorities to implement conservation plans and monitor pollution levels regularly. These directives aimed to restore the health of the Yamuna and prevent further degradation. The tribunal's interventions have been vital in addressing the pollution crisis and promoting sustainable management of this crucial water resource.

Lal Kuan Stone Crushers Case:

In the Lal Kuan Stone Crushers case, the National Green Tribunal (NGT) ordered the closure of several stone crushing units in Lal Kuan, Uttar Pradesh, in 2014. These units were operating without proper environmental clearances and were found to be causing severe air pollution, resulting in significant health issues for local residents, including respiratory problems. The tribunal's

decision emphasized the need for industrial compliance with environmental norms and prioritized public health and environmental protection over unregulated industrial activities. This case highlighted the NGT's role in enforcing environmental regulations and mitigating industrial pollution.

Goa Foundation vs. Union of India:

In the case of Goa Foundation vs. Union of India, the National Green Tribunal (NGT) suspended all mining activities in the state of Goa in 2012. This decision followed petitions by environmental groups highlighting illegal mining practices that were causing extensive environmental degradation, including deforestation and water pollution. The NGT emphasized the need for sustainable mining practices and proper environmental clearances before mining operations could resume. This landmark ruling had a significant impact on Goa's mining industry, setting a precedent for stringent enforcement of environmental laws and ensuring sustainable development in mineral-rich regions.

Delhi Air Pollution Case:

In the Delhi Air Pollution case, the National Green Tribunal (NGT) issued several directives to combat severe air pollution in the national capital. The tribunal banned the sale of diesel vehicles older than 10 years and petrol vehicles older than 15 years, restricted construction activities during high pollution periods, and prohibited the burning of waste in open areas. These measures aimed to improve air quality and protect public health from hazardous levels of air pollution. The NGT's proactive approach in addressing Delhi's air pollution crisis underscored its role in enforcing environmental regulations and promoting sustainable urban development practices.

Kudankulam Nuclear Power Plant Case:

In the Kudankulam Nuclear Power Plant case, the National Green Tribunal (NGT) upheld the environmental clearance granted to the nuclear power plant in Tamil Nadu, subject to strict compliance with safety and environmental norms. The tribunal emphasized the importance of adequate safeguards to mitigate potential environmental impacts and ensure the safety of local communities. The NGT's decision balanced the need for energy security with environmental protection, highlighting its role in scrutinizing large-scale infrastructure projects to uphold ecological integrity and public safety. This case showcased the NGT's approach to promoting sustainable development while safeguarding environmental interests..

POSCO India Project Case:

In the POSCO India Project case, the National Green Tribunal (NGT) suspended the environmental clearance granted to the proposed steel plant in Odisha in 2013. The tribunal cited

inadequate environmental impact assessments and non-compliance with forest rights as reasons for its decision. The project, one of the largest foreign direct investment proposals in India, faced opposition from local communities and environmental groups due to concerns over its potential ecological and social impacts. The NGT's ruling underscored the importance of thorough environmental assessments and community participation in decision-making processes concerning large-scale industrial projects.

M. C. Mehta vs. Union of India:

In the *M. C. Mehta vs. Union of India* case, the National Green Tribunal (NGT) continued its involvement in the long-standing litigation concerning pollution in the Taj Trapezium Zone (TTZ) near the Taj Mahal. The tribunal issued directives to industries to reduce pollution levels, particularly from coal-based industries, to protect the iconic monument from environmental degradation. The NGT's interventions aimed to preserve the architectural and cultural heritage of the Taj Mahal while ensuring compliance with environmental norms, highlighting its role in safeguarding national treasures through stringent environmental oversight and enforcement measures. These cases illustrate the NGT's critical role in enforcing environmental laws, protecting natural resources, and ensuring sustainable development in India.

Impact on Environmental Jurisprudence

Strengthening Environmental Law Enforcement:

The establishment of the NGT has significantly strengthened the enforcement of environmental laws in India. The tribunal's orders and judgments have created a deterrent effect, compelling industries and individuals to comply with environmental regulations. Its proactive approach has filled the gaps in the traditional legal system and ensured that environmental offenders are held accountable.

Promoting Public Participation:

The NGT has promoted public participation in environmental decision-making by providing a platform for individuals and civil society organizations to raise their concerns. The tribunal's accessibility and transparent procedures have empowered citizens to play an active role in environmental protection, fostering a culture of environmental stewardship.

Development of Environmental Jurisprudence:

The NGT has contributed to the development of environmental jurisprudence in India through its progressive and landmark judgments. Its interpretations of environmental laws and principles, such as the "polluter pays" principle and the "precautionary principle," have enriched the legal discourse and set precedents for future cases. The tribunal's decisions have also influenced

policy-making and regulatory frameworks, leading to more robust environmental governance.

Challenges and Criticisms:

The National Green Tribunal (NGT) in India, despite its pivotal role in environmental justice, grapples with various challenges and criticisms. One of the foremost challenges is the effective implementation of its orders. Despite issuing stringent directives on issues like pollution control, forest conservation, and environmental clearances, the actual enforcement often encounters bureaucratic hurdles, delays, and inadequate follow-up mechanisms at the state and local levels. This results in a gap between the tribunal's rulings and their on-ground impact, undermining its effectiveness.

Criticism has also arisen regarding the NGT's jurisdiction and scope. Some stakeholders argue that the tribunal occasionally oversteps its mandate by intervening excessively in developmental projects, which they claim impedes economic growth. This tension between environmental conservation and development priorities underscores a broader debate on regulatory balance in India. Critics contend that while protecting the environment is crucial, stringent NGT rulings sometimes lead to project delays or cancellations, impacting sectors like infrastructure, mining, and industrial development.

Moreover, the NGT faces operational challenges such as backlog of cases and a shortage of expert members, which can delay justice delivery. The tribunal's functioning across its regional benches also varies, with concerns about consistency and expertise in handling complex environmental issues persisting.

Addressing these challenges requires concerted efforts to strengthen enforcement mechanisms, clarify jurisdictional boundaries, and enhance coordination among stakeholders. Finding a balance that ensures robust environmental protection while facilitating sustainable development remains a pressing issue for the NGT and India's environmental governance framework.

Conclusion:

The National Green Tribunal has emerged as a pivotal institution in India's environmental governance framework. Its role in adjudicating environmental disputes, enforcing laws, and promoting public participation has been instrumental in advancing environmental protection. While challenges remain, the NGT's contributions to environmental jurisprudence and its proactive stance in addressing environmental issues underscore its importance. As environmental challenges continue to evolve, the NGT's role will be crucial in ensuring a sustainable and healthy environment for future generations.

By maintaining a balance between environmental protection and developmental needs, the NGT can continue to uphold the principles of justice and sustainability, fostering a harmonious coexistence between nature and society.

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